

A General Overview of Multicultural Design Research Challenges Within Higher Education

Dina Lutfi¹

Department of Graphic Design and Multimedia, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University

ABSTRACT: Design in of itself addresses culture and different aspects of it through the use of different media. However, research and writing about those aspects of culture are considered challenging across different design disciplines due to limited familiarity about their potential and possibilities, in addition to inexperience, and considerations about its usefulness to design processes and outcomes. This paper focuses on highlighting the importance of multicultural research and writing in design, and takes a closer look at the different approaches and methods that may be utilized toward improving multicultural design research and writing within higher education. The paper also recommends familiarizing design professionals with research that stems from cultural practices to more effectively connect visual and written communication.

Key words: Multicultural Design Research, Design Education, Design Writing, Research Culture

[Introduction](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

One of the biggest hurdles that students, educators, and design professionals face is effectively designing for cultural diversity, in addition to pinpointing the value of writing about creative cultural experiences (Buchanan, 2001). Educational research in the field of design is also considered as separate from everyday life (Design-based research: An emerging paradigm for educational inquiry 2003). In design, and other disciplines, research stems from ideas that require investigation from different vantage points to determine how outcomes can be utilized and potentially evaluated (Yilmaz, 2013). There are several significant reasons why designers and educators may consider researching and writing about different cultures, such as to offer new perspectives on design practice, and theory development.

Multicultural design research and writing provides focus in various ways: firstly, design as a practical field demands that a theoretical framework be fully determined before moving forward with practical work. Secondly, research and writing can positively impact the designing for a given culture by unveiling theoretical inconsistencies and unmet needs more effectively than simple analytical processes that are unsupported by practical applications. Thirdly, the goal-oriented nature of design as a field provides a viable space for new theory development, which feeds into practical work about cultures. Designers' experiences are ingrained within visual culture, therefore, it is important to overcome the perceived gap between visual and written communication. This can occur by making research and writing a

¹ Assistant Professor, Graphic Design and Multimedia, College of Design, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, Saudi Arabia. Email: dal2164@tc.columbia.edu

regular occurrence within the design profession, education, and knowledge acquired through our lived experiences (Rice, 2015 and Williams, 2018).

One long-standing issue within circles of design scholars is the dependence of designers on research methodologies and tools often used by social scientists, historians, and those in non-creative disciplines. Another argument posed is that graphic design publications are normally reliant on high quality images in favor of text or consequently a true understanding of the culture at hand (Thomson, 1993). This was true in the past and is still prominent in the digital age through catalogue-like publications that document aesthetics, but lack critical perspectives on cultural design outcomes and their origins. However, the number of practicing graphic designers who publish books and articles has been increasing (Chi, 2007). These developments may encourage educators, students, and future designers to contribute to design scholarship in ways that are more focused on cultural understanding.

This paper recommends the use of research and writing approaches that can be utilized within higher education and beyond to support multicultural design writing—while many of the findings in this article emerged from graphic design, the information can be useful across other design areas.

Common Challenges and Advantages in Multicultural Design Research and Writing

To highlight the state of design research within educational institutions and beyond, I conducted a survey with sixty college graphic design students from different countries, thirty practitioners who have been working as graphic design professionals for at least three years in addition to nineteen graphic design faculty members. The survey consisted of multiple open-ended questions such as asking participants to define what design is, what their cultural roles are as designers, their understanding of design research and writing, and identifying design's connection to investigating and portraying cultures. Only a small percentage of students argued that writing about design and culture are as important as the creative outcome, while most describe design as an aesthetic and intuition-based profession that does not require knowledge about various cultures. Most of the practitioners agreed that research is important to support multicultural design projects, but writing is not essential. While some educators found the exploration of cultures in research and writing to be significant, they expressed they do not have the time to conduct such research to their teaching workloads.

The position of multicultural design scholarship within academic settings can be a cause for tension when creative individuals are encouraged to conduct research using methods used in scientific fields rather than methods geared toward design disciplines (Collins & Bielaczyc, 2004). Designers have worked within their disciplines for years before the word “research” became prominent; writing about design was not considered part of the job description, and it still is not always mandatory beyond academia. Over the years, it has not been uncommon for students, educators, and practitioners to perceive writing in art and design as more difficult than in other disciplines (Orr & Blythman, 2002).

A common response among my students—when asked why they chose design as a major—is that design is a field that encompasses different cultures but does not require test taking, reading, or writing. Higher education places more importance on portfolios rather than

on students' abilities to orally and textually communicate facets of culture. Another major factor distancing designers from multicultural research opportunities is the absence of experience and momentum; the longer one hesitates and refrains from writing about design, the more impossible it seems. In order to research and write about culture, designers need to understand what research can entail. Richard Buchanan states, "No one seems to be sure what design research means. Should design research follow the model of traditional academic disciplines, or should it seek a new model, based on the intimate connection among theory, practice, and production that is the hallmark of design?" (1999, p. 74)

The literature on conducting research within academia confirms that one of the most common complaints among educators is that teaching loads hold them back from research (Nur-tegin, Venugopalan & Young, 2020). Design practitioners also some times face the inability to implement the findings of multicultural educational research to design outcomes due to the breadth of scope. This is mostly because the research conducted was not generated to serve a practical purpose, but a theoretical one. An argument in favor of design research and writing is the direct involvement of researchers in the betterment of education. Designer-researchers immersed in different cultures are not only in a position to write about their findings, but to also improve upon teaching pedagogies that serve future designers and the needs of evolving educational systems. Writing is not only useful during the design process, but any outcomes that result from a design process can be researched as carriers of social value that create communicative opportunities (Dant, 2008).

The Educational Significance of Multicultural Design Research

Graphic design can be viewed as a "sense creating activity" (Krippendorff, 1989, p.9). It encompasses planning and aesthetics as its foundation and becomes meaningful when the outcome is positioned where it belongs—in the hands and minds of the desired target audience. Within the field of visual communication, the scope of knowledge has mainly been published in the form of writings that analyze design outcomes and how-to-books directed at nurturing the practical experiences of the professional graphic designer. It is rare to find writing by the designers who created the aesthetics, and this partly because designers do not always have editorial control of their own work regardless of the area of culture being explored.

Authorship, however, plays a role in stimulating research and design activities (Bayazit, 2004). The designer-as-author holds the potential to destabilize the belief that designers do not engage in cultural research and writing often enough. Frequent research and writing can bring about positive personality changes, such as "decreased self-doubt..." (Boice & Jones, 1984, p.573) Efficient rhetorical communication permits people to connect to one another through expressiveness, discovery, awareness, and social understanding. The act of publishing cultural knowledge offers rewards such as becoming more visible within the design field, but the idea behind design research and writing is not only the gratification of seeing your own name in print. One of the most effective ways to truly become an expert in your own field is to contribute to it, "writing ultimately becomes important not only because of what it does for others but also for what it does for oneself." (Boice & Jones, 1984, p.567)

In many graphic design programs—especially within undergraduate curricula—research leans towards creating mood boards for inspiration rather than methods that are systematically and continuously working with cultural participants, audiences, and end users

as a means of utilizing their responses to improve upon the design outcomes (McDonagh and Storer, 2004). Research and writing ultimately lead designers and audiences to determine what kind of cultural and social values a design holds from ideation to production, and eventually consumption. Such conclusions make reflection and critical writing all the more significant to a designer's education and professional practice (Miller, 2010). One way to ease students into writing about their design findings is to 'engage from a multidisciplinary perspective by exposing them to various perspectives that guide processes and outcomes; these could be geographic, social, and even environmental (Williams & Reiger, 2015). Discussion, structured analysis, and research assignments may encourage students to consider how design can respond to questions, and suggest alternatives to dominant cultural practices. For example, Teal Triggs (2011) argues for the importance of documenting graphic design history in ways that move it from a mere record of design artifacts to a tool that serves to inform design today. They may also assist in a richer understanding of the role of design as a mediator between people and the world. Additionally, historical perspectives in design research can lead the way to developing present and future outcomes.

The Benefits of Design Research and Writing

Within educational settings, it is possible that much of the design processes educators and students engage in is invisible because it is not documented in writing (Daichendt, 2014). Clients and audiences do not usually have an opportunity to see what has occurred between a designer's research and the finished result, which leads to a denial of cultural synthesis altogether. The sparse written documentation leads to missed opportunities for discussion and input that could help improve upon design outcomes and their reception.

Jon Kolko (2010) argues that design research and writing are highly dependent on synthesis, "While other aspects of the design process are visible to non-designers (such as drawing, which can be observed and generally grasped even by non-designers), synthesis is often a more insular activity, one that is less understood, or even hidden from view." (p.15) As designers work, they are often consumed with processing the topic at hand, and will arrive a tangible visual representation of their deliberation. Part of the struggle designers face is putting their visual research into words since some may assume that their own subjectivity would not warrant any written documentation in the larger scope of cultures. But design research and writing is not about right versus wrong; it is an exploration to improve upon previous outcomes. There is a sense of increased "social responsibility" attached to writing about design; it provides credibility, strengthens their competency, and solidifies the "cultural legitimacy" of their designs (Williams & Reiger, 2015, p.17). Making sense of design in written form helps designers develop their practices and offers them the chance to play a role in a more collective design synthesis (Kolko, 2010). Design disciplines consist of information and knowledge that is made relatable, engaging, and interactive through different media and contexts, and research can assist in arriving at the best possible outcomes.

Similarly, design knowledge can be made relatable in exciting and renewable ways. According to Nigel Cross (1999), it is important not to downplay the value of cultural design research since "many of the most valued achievements of humankind are works of design, including anonymous, vernacular design as well as the 'high design' of professionals." (p.6) Consequently, one of the most valued subjects to research as designers is not limited to what people design, but also how they design and reflect upon their work. Although design

research depends on content and context, designers can still find various methods that benefit their processes. For example, empirical investigations of designers' behavior could be a research topic that encompasses theoretical reflections on design abilities within a given context to improve upon design education and practice. The generally qualitative nature of design research provides room for moving beyond the idea of problems and solutions to reflections and improvements within different cultures.

Cultural Design Research and Writing Approaches

Three types of research can prove useful to designers: pure, original, and secondary research. Pure research can be utilized to learn something new by studying a subject without a systematic plan in place. Those looking to find information that has not been uncovered yet can engage in original research. The third type, secondary research, focuses on analyzing and comparing findings from other existing studies to arrive at "a clearer understanding of the material or possibly new insights." (Daichendt, 2014, p.13) Designers possess a wide expertise when it comes to making and communicating in relation to interdisciplinary knowledge (Van de Weijer and Van Cleempoel and Heynen 2014). It is some times a design researcher's inclination to root design research within other disciplines such as science; however, design already has its own intellectual culture and has for many years.

Multicultural design research can be considered a design act in itself, and connecting with other disciplines creates new knowledge among different research practitioners and readership given design's position of being a practice is always centered on other subjects. But while it is acceptable to be inspired by other disciplines, rigor needs to be established within one's own profession in order to foster a stronger specialized research culture.

Case studies are research tools that are generated from design processes; their shared history plays a role in connecting theory and practice in different fields (Breslin & Buchanan, 2008). They can be useful as references for future design outcomes, and offer a point of departure for those interested in design innovation. Educators, students, and practitioners who struggle with design writing may utilize cultural case studies regularly as a way to inspire their own writing. While case studies may not always clarify the author's process of analysis or determine what future decisions could be made, they can connect designers to real life situations and phenomena "in a way that helps to sharpen thinking and inform decision-making." (Breslin & Buchanan, 2008, p.37) The structure of studies resembles the design process in terms of specifying a topic or problem, making a hypothesis, collecting data, making observations, and telling a story. Multicultural case studies can also become more effective as a research tool when design educators follow a more conversational approach. Having dialogues with students removes them from the position of separating theory from practice; it helps them become better at reflection, which ultimately impacts their written communication about cultural design.

Design authorship remains an important part of being a designer. Self-authored graphic design gives designers power to play prominent roles in generating meaningful content, and not only visual form. In academia, self-authored design holds a special position since it intersects with diverse disciplines, which offers many opportunities for integrative studies (McCarthy & de Almeida, 2002). Within design education, courses are normally structured as studios with hands-on activities playing a central role; such a structure encourages those involved to learn by doing. More developed programs, however,

incorporate courses on design history, theory, and criticism in order to motivate students to debate, read, and write.

The inclusion of multicultural theoretical frameworks compliments studio activities, and ultimately the design outcomes. When it comes to self-authorship, students' exploration into initiating their own design content, personal expression, and pinpointing "niche" target audiences all filter into the role all designers can partake in generating "alternative cultures" and "amplifying the fields's conceptual framework, while putting the strictly market-driven concerns of traditional senior portfolios into a broader perspective." (McCarthy & de Almeida, 2002, p.105) While such approaches in design education are usually reserved for graduate studies, self-authorship can be integrated into undergraduate design curriculums to create stronger involvement in specialized areas of theoretical thinking, such as semiotics, technological advancements in software and their applications, design history, semantics, critical theory, in addition to exposure to aesthetics in all its forms and manifestations (Bestley & McNeil, 2022). These areas of study will serve students and future designers as a mode of involvement in interdisciplinary thinking and consequently, cultural design research and writing.

There are different approaches designers can use to further their own vested interests in a topic through commentaries on a particular issue or in analytical documentation of observations. Within the context of education, asking students to use their own experiences can be a way to situate designers in their research stressing the motto "you write best what you know more," which also rings true when it comes to design (McCarthy & de Almeida, 2002, p.112). Exploring different writing genres or exercises that are tailored to design students' needs may be helpful in providing familiarity with writing. For example, my senior students often struggle to choose a topic for a graduation project, but they find it helpful when conducting an exercise where they narrow down their choices to three topics of cultural interest and write short justifications about what makes the ideas worthwhile for different target audiences. They then proceed to create mind maps containing detailed information such as objectives, audience needs, and possible outcomes— regarding each topic—that would then assist them in structuring their design process. Students may also be encouraged to take visual and textual notes, keeping a notebook or sketchbook is useful to design and research processes alike since they are familiar tools for brainstorming and developing ideas while removing some of the intimidation of writing formally (Orr & Blythman, 2002).

Research methods in design can range from surveying existing design work to more complex processes such as the analysis of cultural and social factors associated with design products and their uses (Roth, 1999). Design practice and research utilizes various methods extracted from behavioral and social sciences as well as other aspects such as the business of design and market research. It is essential to note that the extent to which design research plays a role in any given design process is highly dependent on the scope and size of the design establishment and its capabilities (O'Grady & O'Grady, 2017).

The lack of a wider research culture leads to confusion regarding what criteria or models can be used to undergo design research. The debate about the nature of design research can be positive since it may lead to exploring different approaches. For example, design educators and practitioners, argue for a creative-based research that focuses solely on the culmination of the artifact as a valid research approach—moving research away from

a more scientific approach. Such approaches are highly similar to the undergraduate approach to design education, which requires preliminary research to achieve an outcome that is informed and intentional. Some designers and educators may also consider traditional research to be dull and unlike design; therefore, they may aim for approaches that focus on visual research.

Different discourses have emerged as design continues to evolve; one such area is known as design studies, which focuses on “objects and processes from the perspective of critical theory and humanistic inquiry.” (Roth, 1999, p.19) There is a notable distinction between design research and design studies; while design research is project-oriented, design studies is a scholarly area that moves beyond reflecting on form to an interdisciplinary process that centers on “complex systems.” It can draw upon sociology, literature, anthropology and philosophy—to name a few (West, 2016). Within design disciplines, design studies can be beneficial in situating design within a larger theoretical context, which may lead to more effective design outcomes. However, the gap between design writing and practice still needs to be bridged further.

Approaches to design research and writing can be divided into expressive and pragmatic (Buchanan 2013 and Melles 2008). Design that is expressive can be characterized as memorable and entertaining, on the other hand, pragmatic design is often based on practical information. In reality, design projects have the potential to mix both approaches, however, identifying the distinction between the two can assist in determining which research is most appropriately undertaken, and can also be helpful in understanding how different research practices can be accessible within the profession (Suri, 2008). Design research and writing generally addresses three different kinds of queries:

1. Generative: which helps designers gain insights and opportunities. A deep understanding of people’s behaviors, emotions, and motivations within their societies, cultures, and lifestyles inspires new design ideas. The key method here is to interpret the understanding of such variables to create new perspectives not seen in everyday life.

2. Evaluative or formative: which is research that provides continuous learning throughout the process of dealing with questions and ideas as they appear. Designers share their design frameworks from the initial stages through the prototyping phases to assess people’s responses as a way to revise and to refine their work. But rather than engage with evaluative research as an objective test, it is usually more beneficial to engage with people through interactions that include co-designing and co-discovery—in other words, leaving the design process more open-ended (Aitamurto & Holland, 2015). This can lead to in-depth dialogues that are supported by both designers’ and participants’ critical thinking (Hay, Kim and Roy 2005). Design research and writing dissolves the boundaries between theory and practice. When supported with “evaluation-oriented research” it carries with it possibilities to further designers’ understanding of educational systems and how they can impact practice (Edelson, 2002, p.107).

3. Predictive research helps in estimating the potential of a design opportunity even if some information or variables are missing. Such activities focus on looking forward to approximate the potential of future design opportunities.

4. Multicultural design research also entails changing the way we design; this means getting out in the world and observing design-related environments, having conversations with customers and stakeholders, and the willingness to explore unfamiliar territory inside and outside of the studio (Poynor, 2009; Samura 2017). The establishment and continuous development of design reference centers would be helpful to researchers on all levels. Additional information can be generated through different discovery-oriented research activities, for example, experimental research and critical analysis of existing and past design work (Davis, 2016; Ross, 2018). Communication networks are necessary to support researchers' efforts and to circumvent duplication. These are only a few examples of how design research can continuously shape design into a more thoughtful and meaningful practice.

2. Conclusion

Educational institutions and professional designers can benefit from clearly defining the ways in which multicultural design research and writing is important. No one design school or studio is responsible for research in every area of a design discipline. Simply put, creating a research scope that focuses on specific areas would be a fruitful beginning; this provides ways for different institutions and organizations to compliment one other in research and writing interests. In these particular situations, however, a distinction needs to be made between undergraduate, graduate, and professional approaches to research and writing. Graduate and professional research need not be perceived as a mere continuation of undergraduate studies, and this mindset may impact how research is carried out in a more advanced and varied manner.

Multicultural design research for educators, students, and practitioners can include deeper contemplation upon the possibilities and limits of design scholarship to identify the dimensions within design practices. Another recommendation that can serve design research further is the identification of specific topics and questions, rather than broader areas of design; this can lead to more clarity when working within the framework of multidisciplinary approaches in design research. There is a need for developmental support that is specific to design specializations, rather than generalized pathways that depend on scientific research.

Further research can focus on how designers may become better cultural researchers and writers beyond higher education systems. Evidently, educators, their students, and practitioners do not possess the same experiences, but the knowledge and practices—that occur inside and outside of the classroom—can foster a shared research and writing culture that build upon and documents design experiences across cultures.

3. References

1. Aitamurto, T., Holland, D., & Hussain, S. (2015). The Open Paradigm in Design Research. *Design Issues*, 31(4), 17–29. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43830428>
2. Bayazit, N. (2004). Investigating Design: A Review of Forty Years of Design Research. *Design Issues*, 20(1), 16–29. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1511952>
3. Bestley, R., & McNeil, P. (2022). *Visual research an introduction to research methods in graphic design*. Bloomsbury.
4. Boice, R., & Jones, F. (1984). Why Academicians Don't Write. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 55(5), 567–582. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1981822>

5. Buchanan, R. (1996). book review: 'Elements of Design'. *Design Issues*, 12(1).
6. Buchanan, R. (2001). *Design Research and the New Learning*. *Design Issues*, 17(4), 3–23. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1511916>
7. Buchanan, K. T. (2013). *Creative Practice and Critical Reflection: Productive Science in Design Research*. *Design Issues*, 29(4), 17–30.
8. Breslin, M., & Buchanan, R. (2008). On the Case Study Method of Research and Teaching in Design. *Design Issues*, 24(1), 36–40.
9. Chi, L. (2007). Translations between Design Research and Scholarship. *Journal of Architectural Education (1984-)*, 61(1), 7–10. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40480731>
10. Collins, A., Joseph, D., & Bielaczyc, K. (2004). *Design Research: Theoretical and Methodological Issues*. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 13(1), 15–42.
11. Corazzo, J., Harland, R. G., Honnor, A., & Rigley, S. (2019, November 13). The Challenges for Graphic Design in Establishing an Academic Research Culture: Lessons from the Research Excellence Framework 2014. *The Design Journal*, 23(1), 7–29.
12. Cross, N. (1999). *Design Research: A Disciplined Conversation*. *Design Issues*, 15(2), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1511837>
13. Dant, T. (2008). *Material culture in the social world: Values, activities, lifestyles*. Open Univ. Press.
14. Davis, M. (2016) 'Tenure and Design Research: A Disappointingly Familiar
15. Discussion' *Design and Culture* Vol.8(1): pp.123–131
16. Daichendt, G. J. (2014). *Artist-scholar: Reflections on writing and research*. Intellect Books.
17. Edelson, D. C. (2002). *Design Research: What We Learn When We Engage in Design*. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 11(1), 105–121.
18. Harland, R. (2011, January). The Dimensions of Graphic Design and Its Spheres of Influence. *Design Issues*, 27(1), 21–34. https://doi.org/10.1162/desi_a_00054
19. Hay, K. E., Kim, B., & Roy, T. C. (2005). Design-Based Research: More than Formative Assessment? An Account of the Virtual Solar System Project. *Educational Technology*, 45(1), 34–41.
20. Kolko, J. (2010). Abductive Thinking and Sensemaking: The Drivers of Design Synthesis. *Design Issues*, 26(1), 15–28.
21. Krippendorff, K. (1989). On the Essential Contexts of Artifacts or on the Proposition That 'Design Is Making Sense (Of Things).' *Design Issues*, 5(2), 9–39. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1511512>
22. McCarthy, S., & de Almeida, C. M. (2002). Self-Authored Graphic Design: A Strategy for Integrative Studies. *Journal of Aesthetic Education*, 36(3), 103–116. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3333601>
23. Melles, G. (2008). New Pragmatism and the Vocabulary and Metaphors of Scholarly Design Research. *Design Issues*, 24(4), 88–101.
24. Miller, D. (2010). *Material culture and mass consumption*. Blackwell.
25. Nur-tegin, K., Venugopalan, S., & Young, J. (2020). Teaching Load and Other Determinants of Research Output Among University Faculty. *The American Economist*, 65(2), 300–311. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27130000>
26. O'Grady, V. J., & O'Grady, V. K. (2017). *A designer's research manual: Succeed in design by knowing your clients and what they really need*. Rockport Publishers.
27. Orr, S., & Blythman, M. (2002). The Process of Design is Almost Like Writing an Essay. *The Writing Center Journal*, 22(2), 39–54.
28. Poynor, R. (2009) 'Borderline' *Eye* 71 (18), <http://www.eyemagazine.com/feature/article/borderline>
29. Roth, S. (1999). The State of Design Research. *Design Issues*, 15(2), 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1511839>
30. Samura, M. (2017). A Tale of Two Settings: Rethinking Methods and Approaches for Diversity Research. *Humboldt Journal of Social Relations*, 39, 43–50.
31. Suri, J. F. (2008). *Informing Our Intuition: Design Research For Radical Innovation*. *Rotman Magazine*, 53–57.
32. Thomson, E. M. (1993). THE LITERATURE OF GRAPHIC DESIGN. *Art Documentation*:

- Journal of the Art Libraries Society of North America, 12(1), 7–11.
33. The Design-Based Research Collective. (2003). Design-Based Research: An Emerging Paradigm for Educational Inquiry. *Educational Researcher*, 32(1), 5–8. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3699927>
 34. Triggs, T. (2011). Graphic Design History: Past, Present and Future. *Design Issues*, 27(1), 3–6.
 35. Van de Weijer, M., Van Cleempoel, K., & Heynen, H. (2014). Positioning Research and Design in Academia and Practice: A Contribution to a Continuing Debate. *Design Issues*, 30(2), 17–29.
 36. Rice, J. (2015). Para-Expertise, Tacit Knowledge, and Writing Problems. *College English*, 78(2), 117–138.
 37. Ross, R. (2018) 'Producing Knowledge with Billboards: Graphic Design & Research' *Design and Culture*
 38. West, R. E. (2016). Breaking Down Walls to Creativity Through Interdisciplinary Design. *Educational Technology*, 56(6), 47–52.
 39. Williams, W. A., & Rieger, J. (2015). A Design History of Design: Complexity, Criticality, and Cultural Competence. *RACAR: Revue d'art Canadienne / Canadian Art Review*, 40(2), 15–21.
 40. WILLIAMS, A. D. (2018). 'I Don't Know What to Write': Para-expertise and Student Writing. *The English Journal*, 108(1), 52–58.
 41. Yilmaz, K. (2013). Comparison of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Traditions: epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences. *European Journal of Education*, 48(2), 311–325.